

Preserving Computational Workflows

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Abstract—Software workflows describing complex software setups for compute-intensive research disciplines already improve standardization, foster re-use, and simplify re-execution. Re-execution and re-use of these workflows usually aim for a rather short, active research period. Keeping these workflows usable and re-executable for longer time spans (e.g., at least ten years after a research project ended) is a more difficult challenge, as software and its runtime platform (e.g., operating system and hardware) typically have shorter life-cycles. In order to improve long-term re-execution of scientific workflows, we investigate how preservation activities of software can be embedded into the development and usage life-cycle of computational workflows. We have developed means for automated archiving and rewriting of CWL workflows to ensure long-term re-execution using emulation. We show how archiving CWL workflows can be integrated into contemporary Continuous Integration systems to achieve Continuous Preservation.

Index Terms—workflow preservation, CWL, emulation, container

I. INTRODUCTION

Research data management (RDM) is a major step-stone to keep computational research comprehensible, re-usable, and reproducible. With the FAIR data principles [1], abstract concepts have been developed to be implemented into RDM frameworks and services. (Long-term) preservation aspects of research data, e.g., bit preservation, cataloging, (domain specific) meta-data, publication, and byte-stream access can be considered as conceptually solved and are mostly implemented in productive setups. However, with growing size and complexity of research data, data processing tasks also became more complex, e.g., requiring (tailored) software chained to computational workflows. Though, preserving the digital "scientific context" is an even more difficult task [2] while increasingly necessary for re-using or reproducing research results.

As these software setups reached a level of complexity, they are now modeled and represented as *workflows* to improve standardization, foster re-use and especially portability. Workflows provide machine-actionable descriptions of a multi-step computational process, orchestrating tasks, resources, as well as data in- and output. FAIR principles for software [3] and workflows [4] are currently discussed but especially (long-term) aspects of "re-use" still require conceptual and implementation work. While concepts for preserving (scientific) software, citation of software, and re-execution of software are in principle well understood, the ability of re-using, reproducing, or replicating of software-based methodology is

not yet (fully) embedded into typical RDM services and more importantly also not very well embedded into planning and execution of scientific projects. For active research projects, simplified access, integration into contemporary infrastructure, and usability are the dominant focus, while planning continuous, long-term access and especially preparations for long-term re-use are of lesser importance. Tasks or other activities targeted towards long-term re-use are usually not integrated into daily work and are postponed or scheduled for late phases of a research project. Postponing these tasks, however, may lead to a loss of knowledge and configuration details about the necessary software setup necessary to ensure proper re-use especially due to a lack of resources (and interest) when research projects end.

To close this gap between active research and future re-use, in this paper we investigate how preservation planning and preservation action can be embedded into scientific workflow development. By integrating infrastructure addressing long-term access to software using emulation and reproducible research into current workflows, we are working towards the concept of *continuous preservation* and *continuous access*, with the goal that any RDM step is connected with a preservation strategy in an automated way, e.g., a successful commit of code or a successful run of a workflow will trigger a pipeline of events such that code dependencies are collected and maintained. This snapshot of the workflow can be re-run on-demand using dedicated long-term infrastructure.

We have chosen scientific workflows as an example use-case as these offer important insights into the technical variety, explicit and implicit infrastructure requirements, and challenges of computational research practice. As an example, we have implemented a prototype with an existing workflow framework. We chose the Common Workflow Language (CWL) [5] as the specification for which we want to integrate the system with the emulation-based preservation and access framework Emulation-as-a-Service (EaaS)¹.

II. RELATED WORK

Preserving scientific processes and capturing scientific tool-chains and workflows have been active topics both for research data management as well as for digital libraries and preservation communities. For instance, the preservation of (business) processes and scientific workflows has been identified as a preservation target and has been formalized from a practical

¹<https://github.com/emulation-as-a-service>

[6] as well as from a planning perspective [7] quite early. Similarly, the concept of research objects (RO) [8] together with a set of tools [9] have been proposed with the goal to create aggregated digital objects containing (exemplary) input-data, a workflow description as well as information regarding the required execution environment and parameters for re-execution in a machine readable (i.e., semantically enriched [10]) format. Rebuilding a sufficient computational environment for re-execution remained a challenge. Even though with the availability of cloud infrastructure, it became possible to share the execution environment as well [11], workflows remained fragile objects [12].

The rise of the container technology (e.g., Docker, Singularity, etc.) made computational software setups more lightweight, portable, and, most importantly, easily reusable [13]. While container technology as well as more sophisticated software packaging (e.g., *Bioconda* [14]) improved portability of software setups, it is not solely sufficient to improve sharing, re-use, and reproduction of computational workflows. A further major step forward was the infrastructure that has been built around container technologies. Container registries (e.g., most prominently *Docker Hub*) made access to containerized software very simple, allowing to “pull” a specific setup through a symbolic identifier from a central repository. On top of this infrastructure, domain-specific specialized software libraries have evolved (e.g., *BioContainers* [15]). Additionally, community platforms like *myExperiments* allow researchers to publish and share their workflows [16].

While the currently available technology and infrastructure supports ongoing, active research, ensuring long-term (re-)execution of workflows requires additional steps. The implicit assumption that resolving and accessing container images from “freemium” repositories will remain possible in the long-term is likely to be challenged, especially for container images that are not anymore part of the scientific *zeitgeist*. Additionally, computer architectures and software environments (e.g., operating system and library versions) change over time, which threatens the ability to re-run pre-packaged and pre-configured software setups [17].

III. PRESERVING WORKFLOWS

The description of a workflow – usually a text-based representation – separates data dependencies and software necessary by individual workflow steps from workflow execution aspects, such as allocating compute resources. In principle, a specific workflow can be executed on a researcher’s laptop computer, in a distributed cloud setup, HPC clusters, or a mixtures of these. Workflow management systems (WfMS) provide the infrastructure to parse descriptions, set up necessary runtime infrastructure, monitor workflow execution, and manage workflow output.

A workflow definition describes the individual steps of a computational workflow. Usually, the description of a workflow step describes the software or tool to be used, e.g., the executable, including how it should be run given a defined input together with expected output. In order to preserve

Fig. 1. Workflow example consisting of four step, where step C’ is the archived version of C. The behavior of C’ is required to be identical to C, to ensure that the output of both workflows is the same.

workflows, the first goal is to capture the individual software environment for each computational step. The software used as well as the required runtime environment have to be transferred into a stable, long-term executable form and archived in an automated way. If automated archiving is not possible, preservation and re-execution risks become visible through this process. Additionally, for workflow execution, it should be possible to switch between the live or production environment and archived workflow steps without changing the workflow’s behavior or semantics (cf. Fig. 1), apart from execution time – due to the emulation overhead, the required execution time will be typically longer. This allows to fully integrate preservation steps with automated execution “pipelines”.

A. Preserving Container-based Software Dependencies

In scientific workflows, workflow steps are usually executed within specified containers. This means that in order to preserve a workflow, its container-based steps need to be preserved in a way that still offers the original functionality and accessibility. Containers virtualize operating system interfaces, such that the container is isolated from the host system and thus, by definition, need to be self-contained, i.e., all software dependencies (libraries, applications, etc.) have to be included within the container image. Consequently, the main content of a container image is a self-contained file-system with installed and configured software components (except the operating system kernel, which is provided by the host system). The remaining external or unresolved software dependencies are the container runtime and the underlying operating system kernel’s application binary interface (ABI).

A container’s technical runtime is composed of two components: a hardware platform (the computer) and software. For long-term access, the hardware component can simply be replaced by an emulated hardware equivalent, which allows containers (together with the vendor specific software dependencies) to be archived such that the containers can remain unchanged over time (cf. Fig 2, middle). The underlying emulators will change over time, due to the changes of the contemporary hardware platforms, such that software runtime may also have to be adapted to the emulator, e.g., if emulated hardware components have changed.

Even though all (Linux) containers are built on top of the same technical foundations [18], today’s popular container implementations, e.g., Docker or Singularity, use different internal representations and configuration formats. Thus, these

Fig. 2. Left: full contemporary software and hardware setup. Middle: hardware is replaced by a hardware equivalent (emulator), software stack remains unchanged. Right: Vendor specific container format is migrated to a generic container representation. Vendor specific runtime is exchange by a generic runtime.

representations require a (vendor) specific technical runtime with the appropriate software version. With respect to long-term maintenance of such user provided objects, these different runtimes need to be maintained over time. A potential future access framework is likely to require adaptations, e.g. for reusing containers with user-provided data, providing interactive access to the contained software process (e.g., to tweak variables), or to access a process’s output for inspection or further processing.

The goal is then to have to preserve only a small number of software runtimes being able to run a large number of preserved containers and a common generic container and configuration representation, which reduces the complexity and simplifies developing access services. By leveraging the fact that all containers consist of a filesystem representation and configuration meta-data, we have implemented a common archive representation of containers together with a workflow to ingest and convert container “flavors” into this common format as part of the EaaS framework. The vendor-specific filesystem representation needs to be “migrated” to an immutable image format at preservation time. Configuration meta-data needs to be captured and converted such that the container bundle can be executed by a common (standard) runtime. In our case, we use *runc*² on top of a minimal Linux system (about 60 MB)³. The container runtime may be adopted over time, e.g., if new features have been added to the container eco-system. However, this usually only applies to new, contemporary containers. Older, already preserved containers can remain unchanged, only the (emulated) hardware might need to be updated.

In order to preserve a software-tool, an interface to the (Emulation-as-a-Service) emulation framework (EaaS) to

transfer the appropriate container into a stable representation is required. To import and run containers in an emulated context, EaaS offers an HTTP-based (REST-like) API. An import request usually contains a reference to a container image in a registry (e.g., Docker Hub) but other import types such as tar archive or similar are also possible. Optionally, a specific container runtime can be chosen. As container image references can point to an OCI image index⁴ consisting of multiple separate single images for different architectures (e.g., x86-64, ARM64) and operating systems, the chosen container runtime determines for which architecture and operating system the container image is imported. Although, currently only a runtime for Linux on x86-64 is supplied, new runtimes for other platforms can be easily added in the future as EaaS supports emulators emulating many different architectures. As EaaS uses emulators to execute the containers, the container runtime platform does not need to match the host platform.

Upon import, if not already specified, the backend determines the unique digest of the container image in its current version and compares it to previously stored digests. Only the digest (together with the target architecture and operating system in case of an OCI image index) uniquely identifies a container image in a certain (fixed) version. If container images are specified using a name and tag only (e.g., `container:latest` or `container:1.0.0`), a snapshot of the current version of the container image is saved. If the container image (with the same tag) is modified, a new version is archived at the next import. If embedded meta-data is available (e.g., in case of Docker), information about the execution environment (e.g., environment variables) and process information (e.g., path to the executable and its arguments) are extracted and saved. In case of a successful import, an *environment ID* is returned to the caller. This ID allows to

²CLI tool for spawning and running containers on Linux according to the OCI Runtime Specification, <https://github.com/opencontainers/runc>

³<https://gitlab.com/emulation-as-a-service/linux-container-base-image/>

⁴<https://github.com/opencontainers/image-spec/blob/7b36cea86235157d78528944cb94c3323ee0905c/image-index.md>

request the container’s metadata, modify the runtime setup if necessary, and most importantly to execute the container. Once a container image is imported, it can be executed either in an interactive session (with access to terminal input/output via a web browser) or as a “headless” compute job. For the purpose of running as part of a workflow, a headless execution is most useful.

B. CWL Workflows

There exist a large number of (partly domain-specific) WfMS [19]. For our study, we have chosen CWL [5] as it is designed to be independent of a specific WfMS. CWL workflows can be specified in an operating-system independent way and can be executed using a *runner* or WfMS that supports CWL, such as Arvados⁵, Toil⁶, CWL-Airflow⁷, REANA⁸, or the reference implementation cwltool⁹. Still, the concepts proposed in this paper should be applicable to other workflow description languages or WfMS.

CWL is a specification that allows to create workflows by chaining multiple command-line tools together. CWL files either specify a *CommandLineTool* or a *Workflow*. A CWL workflow describes the execution order of other CWL files, which can either contain another workflow or a command-line tool. A workflow is executed in combination with a so called job-file that defines the input for the execution. A workflow defines steps which are executed with respect to dependencies of in- and output on other steps. The *CommandLineTool* defines the execution of a given program, script or command (e.g., `./myscript.sh` or `mkdir output`) in the current context. It contains information about the expected input (defined in the job-file) and output, arguments (parameters that are not defined in the job file), etc. To improve portability, a *CommandLineTool* may also contain a *DockerRequirement* which ensures that this tool is executed within a specified Docker container. Upon execution, for CWL files that specify a *CommandLineTool*, the tool will be executed with the provided parameters and its specified output will be returned. If a *Workflow* is specified, each step is executed (possibly, in parallel) where outputs of a step can be used as input for following steps. Fig. 3 depicts an excerpt of a real world CWL example.

In order to support (long-term) re-execution of CWL workflows, we require all non-trivial software tools used in a workflow to be packaged as container images. We can assume that in most cases this requirement is already fulfilled in order to make CWL workflows portable.

C. Executing Preserved Containers in Workflows

As described in Section III-A, the EaaS framework is capable of preserving container-based tools. To make these

⁵<https://arvados.org/>

⁶<https://github.com/DataBiosphere/toil>

⁷<https://github.com/Barski-lab/cwl-airflow>

⁸<https://docs.reana.io/>

⁹<https://github.com/common-workflow-language/cwltool>

preserved tools accessible from a CWL workflow, we developed a script, titled *CWL Wrapper*¹⁰. The wrapper acts as a proxy for running a tool that is available as an EaaS container environment. The wrapper executes the preserved tool through the EaaS API while keeping the exact calling interface and functionality as the original tool, i.e., the wrapper accepts the same input and returns the same output files as the original one. This allows to freely interchange the original tool with the preserved one and vice versa.

To enable CWL integration, we have created a Docker image containing the wrapper script. The wrapper Docker replaces the `DockerRequirement` in a `CommandLineTool`. The wrapper script needs to be called with a configuration file which contains necessary information for tool execution, such as the EaaS *environment ID* identifying the container environment that contains the original tool that is *wrapped*. This configuration file is specified as a `InitialWorkDirRequirement` which tells the CWL runner to create it during execution of the `CommandLineTool`.

When the wrapper script is called during a workflow execution, it packages required input data as a tar archive and uploads it to the EaaS backend, either as general input-data or as `workdir-data` to be stored in the process’s working directory. Afterwards, the wrapper sends a request to the EaaS API endpoint referencing the appropriate environment (container image and runtime) as well as the execution parameters for the container’s process and the reference to the input data, which starts the execution of the preserved tool.

While the tool is running, the wrapper monitors the status of the execution, downloads the result in case of successful completion, and provides the files in a designated output directory, where they can be accessed by the workflow runner.

```
1 class: CommandLineTool
2 baseCommand: [myTool.sh]
3 requirements:
4   DockerRequirement:
5     dockerPull: myContainer:1.0
6 inputs:
7   inputFile:
8     type: File
9   inputBinding:
10    prefix: --file
```

Listing 1: CWL `CommandLineTool` with a `DockerRequirement`

Listing 1 shows a part of an exemplary CWL file that uses a container-based tool, namely **myContainer:1.0**. In line 4, the `DockerRequirement` tells a CWL runner to execute the specified `baseCommand` within a container that is specified by `dockerPull`. When this `CommandLineTool` is executed, the CWL Runner creates a temporary container of the **myContainer:1.0** image. The runner then mounts the `inputFile` into the container. Afterwards, the runner

¹⁰<https://gitlab.com/emulation-as-a-service/experiments/cwl-wrapper>

```

inputs:
  map_otu_table: File
  map_query: File
  map_label: string
  return_dirname: string

outputs:
  out_dir:
    type: Directory?
    outputSource: return_output_dir/out

steps:
  mapseq2biom:
    run: ../mapseq2biom/mapseq2biom.cwl
    in:
      otu_table: map_otu_table
      label: map_label
      query: map_query
    out: [otu_tsv, otu_txt, otu_tsv_notax]

counts_to_hdf5:
  run: ../biom-convert/biom-convert.cwl
  in:
    biom: mapseq2biom/otu_tsv
    hdf5: { default: true }
    table_type: { default: 'OTU table' }
  out: [ result ]

```

```

class: CommandLineTool

hints:
  DockerRequirement:
    dockerPull: quay.io/biocontainers/biom-format:2.1.6--py36_0

baseCommand: [ biom, convert ]

inputs:
  biom:
    type: File?
    format: edam:format_3746 # BIOM
    inputBinding:
      prefix: --input-fp
  ...

outputs:
  result:
    type: File
    outputBinding:
      glob: _hdf5.biom

```

```

map_otu_table:
  class: File
  path: test-input/test-otu

map_query:
  class: File
  path: test-input/test-mapseq
  map_label: 'test'

return_dirname: returnDir

```

Fig. 3. CWL workflow example: simplified version of a classification workflow that is part of the *MGnify pipeline version 5.0* from <https://github.com/EBI-Metagenomics/pipeline-v5>. *workflow.cwl* shows an excerpt of a CWL workflow file. Two steps, *mapseq2biom* and *counts_to_hdf5*, are executed. Each of these steps is defined in separate CWL file, the right side shows parts of the CWL file *mapseq2biom.cwl*. The blue box marks where the CWL workflow calls *mapseq2biom.cwl*. The red box highlights the Docker container that is required for this CWL file. The green boxes display that the output of *mapseq2biom* is passed as input to the next step *counts_to_hdf5*. The yellow boxes show that the YAML file contains information about all necessary inputs that are defined in *workflow.cwl*.

executes the baseCommand **myTool.sh** within the container and supplies potential inputs. In line 10, **--file** is defined as prefix for **inputFile**. This results in the execution of

```
myTool.sh --file path/to/inputFile
```

in the container. After execution, the CWL runner would then retrieve outputs from the container and shutdown the container afterwards.

```

1 class: CommandLineTool
2 baseCommand: [python3, /app/wrapper.py,
3               myTool.sh]
4 requirements:
5   DockerRequirement:
6     dockerPull: ../cwl-wrapper:latest
7     dockerOutputDirectory: /app/output
8 inputs:
9   inputFile:
10    type: File
11    inputBinding:
12      prefix: --file
13 InitialWorkDirRequirement:
14 listing:
15   - entryname: config.json
16     entry: |-
17       {
18         "environmentId": "5fe4bd..."
19       }

```

Listing 2: Rewritten CWL CommandLineTool using the CWL Wrapper

Listing 2 displays how the CWL wrapper can be used CommandLineTool while providing the same functionality as Listing 1. In line 6, the **dockerPull** specifies that the wrapper image should be used. By specifying a **dockerOutputDirectory**, CWL tells the runner in which directory (in the container) it can find the wrapper's output (line 7). Furthermore, in line 2, the **baseCommand** is extended to execute the (python) wrapper script instead of **myTool.sh**. However, **myTool.sh** is passed to the wrapper as an argument, thus it will be passed as an argument to the backend as well. The most simple configuration for the wrapper contains only the environment ID (**5fe4bd...**) of the emulation environment that contains the preserved version of **myContainer:1.0**. In line 15, an **InitialWorkDirRequirement** for such a **config.json** is defined. When executed, the CWL runner generates **config.json** and creates a container of the specified wrapper image. It then mounts both **config.json** and the **inputFile** to the container.

Finally, the runner executes

```
python3 /app/wrapper.py myTool.sh
--file /path/to/inputFile
```

in the wrapper container and mounts both **config.json** and the provided **inputFile** to it. First, the wrapper reads the environment ID from **config.json**. It then identifies the **inputFile** as a file and uploads it to the EaaS backend, which returns a URL that can be used to access the file internally. The wrapper then calls the EaaS API with the specified environment ID, the URL for the input file, and with

`myTool.sh --file path/to/mounted/inputFile` as the arguments that should be executed in the preserved container. After the execution, the wrapper retrieves output files from the backend and copies them to the specified `dockerOutputDirectory`, where the CWL runner can access them.

D. Automated Rewriting of Workflows

With the wrapper script, we have developed an interface to access preserved containers and, in principle, a way to replace containerized tools in a CWL workflow with archived ones. However, manually uploading containers and editing CWL workflows is labor-intensive and error-prone and not a viable solution for larger workflows. In addition to the CWL wrapper, we have developed the CWL rewriter¹¹ with the goal of automatically applying the steps described previously to CWL files. When executed on a CWL workflow, the output of this script is a new (standard compliant) CWL workflow that uses the same input as the original workflow and produces the same results but accesses the preserved containers via the wrapper script instead of using the original containers.

The CWL rewriter takes a single CWL file as its argument and parses it. If that CWL file contains a *CommandLineTool* entry, the following changes are applied:

- 1) exchange the *DockerRequirement* to use the CWL wrapper script,
- 2) prepend `[python3, /app/wrapper.py]` to `baseCommand`,
- 3) add a new *InitialWorkDirRequirement* that creates `config.json`, which contains all necessary information to allow the wrapper to execute the preserved container.

If the input defines a workflow instead, the procedure is applied for each workflow step recursively. If the exemplary CWL file in Listing 1 were rewritten, the result would be the CWL file in Listing 2.

When exchanging the original *DockerRequirement* with the wrapper script, the archived container environment needs to be identified or created. The rewriter uses the *import container EaaS API* with the original Docker image reference to retrieve the necessary information. The EaaS backend is either able to resolve the container (if it was imported already) or will initiate an import. In both cases, an environment ID is returned and stored in the *InitialWorkDirRequirement* that handles the configuration file for the wrapper.

Figure 4 gives an overview of the execution of a rewritten CWL file. It displays that the same job file can be used with both workflows, leading to the same result.

At first, it may seem counter-intuitive to create a second, rewritten workflow that needs to be maintained in parallel to the original workflow. However, the rewriting process can be fully automated, resulting in no additional effort once the pipeline is set up, for an example see Section V.

¹¹<https://github.com/emulation-as-a-service/cwl-rewriter>

E. Modification Justifications

For re-use and most importantly replication purposes, it is required that the archived workflow is equivalent to the original. While it is difficult to formally prove equivalency, modifications made can be justified:

Input, output, or other invocation parameters of a software tool remain unchanged. The archived software tool accepts the exact same inputs as the original one and returns the same output. Furthermore, the software environment of the software tool used in a workflow step has been encapsulated already, by using a container.

If any *InitialWorkDirRequirements* are defined in the original workflow, they are marked as such in `config.json`, which allows the wrapper to be able to distinguish between *InitialWorkDirRequirements* and other input files. Adding an additional *InitialWorkDirRequirements* to configure the EaaS CWL wrapper script does not change the software tool's behavior.

Finally, the invocation of the original `baseCommand` is now indirect and exchanged through the EaaS wrapper script. The original command and all command-line arguments are passed to the wrapper without further modifications and input files are mounted equivalent to their original structure. This results in the exact same invocation of a tool within the preserved container.

The rewriter and wrapper currently utilize Docker for convenience reasons to support existing users. However, the future execution of the wrapper is not limited to the Docker ecosystem. The concepts introduced in this paper would remain relevant, regardless of the container technology used. By adapting the preservation measures outlined in Section III-A, long-term software tool execution can be ensured through emulation. Converting container images from various sources (e.g., Docker, Singularity) to a generic format reduces necessary maintenance work as changes are only needed once for a single, common class of preserved software objects, extending the idea of generalizing emulation environments for simplified long-term preservation to container images and computational workflows. Necessary adaptations might include changes to the generic container runtime, e.g., an updated Linux kernel to accommodate the runtime to a new emulator or porting an existing emulator to a new host platform.

IV. EXAMPLE

To demonstrate the capabilities of the system, we use an existing bioinformatics workflow and execute it and its rewritten version and compare the results. For demonstration purposes, we have simplified and shortened an existing CWL workflow of the *MGNify pipeline version 5.0*¹². The example workflow, together with sample input, can be found on GitHub¹³.

The workflow requires four inputs, `map_otu_table`, `map_label`, `map_query`, and `return_dirname`. The first three inputs are required for the first step, *mapseq2biom*.

¹²<https://github.com/EBI-Metagenomics/pipeline-v5>

¹³<https://github.com/emulation-as-a-service/cwl-example-workflow>

Fig. 4. Execution Overview

The next steps, *counts_to_hdf5* and *counts_to_json*, take two default arguments and the output of *mapseq2biom*, *mapseq2biom/otu_tsv*, as their input. The final step, *return_output_dir*, finally takes the output of all previous steps, as well as *return_dirname* as its input and accumulates the results as the final workflow output. The steps *mapseq2biom*, *counts_to_hdf5*, and *counts_to_json* have a `DockerRequirement` specified in their CWL file. Figure 5 visualizes the workflow via the CWL Viewer¹⁴.

Using the CWL rewriter on *example_workflow.cwl* results in four new files, with the previously described changes (see section III-D) applied. Both the workflow description, *example_workflow.cwl* and the three step descriptions *mapseq2biom*, *counts_to_hdf5*, and *counts_to_json* are rewritten. All specified containers which are not already stored in the backend get imported during the rewriting process. The last step, *return_output_dir*, is not rewritten as it has no `DockerRequirement` specified.

To ensure that the rewritten workflow behaves as the original one, we execute both the original and the rewritten workflow and compare the results. The original workflow creates an output directory with the name specified by *return_dirname*. It contains four files, *_hdf5.biom*, *_json.biom*, *test-mapseq.tsv*, and *test-mapseq.txt*. As the first validation step, we need to ensure that the output files of the rewritten CWL files are identical to those of the original workflow. We execute both the original and the rewritten workflow with the same input, with a different *return_dirname* (which only defines the name of the output directory), so that we can compare the different output directories. After executing both workflows, both directories contain the same four files. The contents match in name, file type and size, only the date of creation

Fig. 5. Visualization of the Example Workflow

differs. Additionally, `cwltool` provides checksum for the results of a workflow. Both workflow results create files with matching checksums, *_hdf5.biom* and *_json.biom* where we can see discrepancies for the checksum. This is due to the creation time of the files being stored within the files, which results in different checksums. However, by using tools such as `git diff`, we can easily validate that the only difference between the files is the creation date, the remainder of each file is equivalent to each other.

V. TOWARDS CONTINUOUS PRESERVATION

Preservation does typically not belong to the most important tasks of a scientific work group. Especially long-term aspects are usually neglected, either due to the lack of awareness (and training) but also as these tasks conflict with typical working patterns. During development, preservation is often not a key aspect as it does not contribute to the direct progress

¹⁴<https://view.commonwl.org/>

of scientific projects but puts additional burden on researchers. Ideally, however, preservation tasks are embedded into development work when the knowledge about inner mechanics, dependencies and usage is still completely available.

Development work nowadays usually happens in Git forges like GitHub, GitLab, or Gitea, which combine the Git version control system with surrounding features like an issue tracker, a container image registry, or a Continuous Integration (CI) system. CI systems differ between Git forges but they generally allow to execute some code each time some event, e.g., a push of new commits to a branch, occurs. The code is running on computational resources provided by the Git forge provider, e.g., on a cloud. This functionality is used to build and test software projects each time a new commit is made and already well-established within various communities.

We thus propose to integrate the preservation step into existing CI systems and workflows and extend them to provide *Continuous Preservation*. Projects might already use a CI workflow to execute a test run of a CWL workflow with some sample data every time a change is made. This moment, where the CWL file was just tested to be runnable including its dependencies in the versions being current at that time, provides a good opportunity to preserve the workflow with all of its dependencies. Even if a CI system is not already used by a project, users will probably have executed the CWL workflow manually before pushing a new commit. The container image versions being current at that time thus represent what users have originally used to execute the CWL workflow and should be used for a most authentic re-execution of the CWL workflow in the future.

To simplify the creation of CI workflows, most Git forges allow users to create re-usable components (called actions in GitHub¹⁵ and, albeit not as widely used, includes in GitLab¹⁶), which can be included as steps in a project's local CI workflow. The CWL rewriter (see section III-D) was thus turned into a GitHub action which accepts the path to a CWL file in the repository to be preserved as input and generates the preserved and wrapped CWL file(s) as artifact output.

The generated artifact containing the wrapped CWL file(s) then has to be preserved itself, which provides a challenge as GitHub defaults to a 90 day retention time for artifacts generated by actions.¹⁷ This means that users might have successfully preserved their CWL workflows but later lost the information connecting the original workflows to EaaS emulation environments. Our current solution is to have the GitHub action commit the preserved and wrapped CWL file(s) directly to the original Git repository (on a separate branch), where the snapshot is safe to be preserved as long as the original Git repository is preserved. At the same time this ensures that any commit in the project's history can be

directly connected to a workflow snapshot without external information.

For the example workflow, we created two GitHub actions¹⁸ that are executed when a commit is pushed: One runs the original workflow, the second one uses the rewriter action to create a new workflow and executes it afterwards. A future step would be to automatically compare the outputs of both actions, to confirm that the results are identical. Artifacts could then be discarded afterwards, as we can guarantee that there is a workflow snapshot that allows us to generate these artifacts again on-demand.

VI. CONCLUSION

Workflows using software are aging differently compared to the research data itself. Re-execution and further reuse of scientific workflows depend very much on the availability and usability of the software used. Especially preparing for retention times that span longer than the typical life-cycle of soft- and hardware requires explicit preservation activities, which are currently not an integral part of computational science development workflows, due to different objectives during the active phase of research. The work and examples presented in this article aim to bridge the gap between the active phase and preservation tasks necessary for long-term re-execution of workflows by directly integrating preservation into the active phase. The approach is not limited to CWL but can easily be extended to other workflow definition languages.

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¹⁸Demonstrated in <https://github.com/emulation-as-a-service/cwl-example-workflow/actions/>.

¹⁵<https://docs.github.com/en/actions/creating-actions>

¹⁶https://docs.gitlab.com/ee/ci/yaml/yaml_optimization.html#use-extends-and-include-together

¹⁷<https://docs.github.com/en/actions/learn-github-actions/usage-limits-billing-and-administration#artifact-and-log-retention-policy>

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